

Does a SARS-CoV-2 Infection Increase the Risk of Dementia? Causal Machine Learning for Predictive Risk Models on Real-World Patient Data

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Abstract. Despite the relative recency of the global pandemic, there is evidence that a SARS-CoV-2 infection may act as a catalyst in the gradual manifestation of neurodegenerative diseases. For example, comparisons of biomarkers before and after an infection revealed signs of changes in brain structure, neuroinflammation and disruptions of the blood-brain barrier. As part of the EU-funded COMMUTE project, we deploy and adapt causal machine learning risk models on real-world data to investigate whether a SARS-CoV-2 infection increases the risk or accelerates the process of developing Alzheimer’s or Parkinson’s disease, and which factors from a patient’s history may play a role in this assumed co-pathology. Any findings are potentially affected by baseline confounding, dependent censoring and death from any cause as a competing risk. We estimate average exposure effects of COVID-19 on event risks with models that address the potential sources of bias via Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (TMLE). Predicted effects undergo a detailed sensitivity analysis with respect to different datasets, alternative control group design and dataset stratification (e.g., by infection wave, age and sex), demonstrating that our data base does not support the hypothesis of a systematic increase of neurodegenerative disease diagnoses in the two-year aftermath of the pandemic. Prospectively, models will be trained to make individualized risk and exposure effect predictions for unseen patients. These models will derive encodings of structured data from electronic health records, e.g., via transformer architectures.

Keywords: Causal machine learning · predictive analytics in healthcare
· AI-aided large-scale cohort data analyses.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Multiple studies with genetic, imaging and clinical study data have indicated a potential link between COVID-19 and the development of neurodegeneration

[1–3]. Two studies even postulated increased risks of Alzheimer’s [4] and Parkinson’s [5] diagnoses as documented in electronic health records in the immediate aftermath of the pandemic. We aim to put the testing of this hypothesis on a more robust footing, using targeted estimation as a state-of-the-art debiasing pipeline for trustworthy effect estimates and analyzing multiple real-life data cohorts from different countries.

In our analyses, the "exposure" is operationalized as the first reported positive test for SARS-CoV-2. The event of interest is the first documented diagnosis of either Alzheimer’s disease, Parkinson’s disease, or unspecified dementia, and treated as a time-to-event outcome.

1.2 Challenges in the real-world data for our application

Multiple application-specific challenges need to be addressed to forestall bias. Firstly, death from any cause shares risk factors with neurodegenerative diseases (age in particular) and can preclude receiving a diagnosis, which makes it a competing risk. Secondly, the subset of cases that is actually detected can be expected to have varied a lot throughout the pandemic (e.g., due to changing testing capacities), causing exposure inconsistency and changing confounding factors over time. Lastly, the available follow-up length for every patient can depend on individual factors, especially on the calendar date of the reported infection.

An overarching problem is that almost everyone in a given cohort can be expected to have had COVID at least once, but not all infections got documented. This makes it difficult to emulate an appropriate control group from observational data. We address this challenge by testing multiple alternative control group designs: Individuals with follow-up *before* the pandemic (Fig. 1), and individuals who got tested, but always negative.

2 Methods

2.1 Data

Current results are based on the UK Biobank, a cross-sectional population study of approx. 500,000 participants from the UK. Approx. 51,000 individuals aged 70 or older qualify as test-detected COVID cases throughout the pandemic, and the pool of controls counts approx. 210,000. There is follow-up available until the end of 2022, which is a good two years after the first wave of the pandemic.

2.2 Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation

We estimate counterfactual cumulative risks in the population (What if everyone in the population had been infected with SARS-CoV-2? What if no one had?) using Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (TMLE) [6]. The main asset of this framework is that it allows combining data-adaptive and flexible estimation

Fig. 1. Pre-pandemic control group design: For the COVID group, the index is the date of the first documented positive test. Index and follow-up length for the control group are chosen to match the age and follow-up length of a sampled patient from the COVID group. If data is available for a control from 2020 on (without confirmed COVID infection), this data is discarded.

via machine learning with desirable statistical properties, i.e., double robustness, semiparametric efficiency, and rigorous statistical inference. We compute initial estimates of event and censoring risks using `SurvivalBoost` [7] with hyperparameters tuned in a cross-validation design, then combine it with propensity estimates for a recursive update loop to get debiased population estimates as suggested by Rytgaard & van der Laan [8] with our in-house library `PyTMLE` [9]. The following potential confounders were included in the analysis: age at index, sex, education level, income status, deprivation index, body mass index, smoking behavior, blood pressure, self-reported sleep behavior, regional air pollution, and history of diabetes, depression, obesity, or cardiovascular diseases.

3 Results

In the UK Biobank, we cannot find further evidence for increased risks of receiving neurodegeneration-related diagnoses on population average in the first two years after the first reported SARS-CoV-2 diagnosis, neither in the whole population of 70+ year olds for any infection wave nor in strata by age or sex. Fig. 2 exemplifies the estimated counterfactual risks for the first (March to August 2020) and the second (September 2020 to May 2021) infection waves and the two control group designs. Even though there is a tendency of increased predicted counterfactual risks if everyone is assumed to have been infected, the confidence intervals between counterfactuals overlap for each configuration at each target time. The higher predicted risks and larger confidence intervals in the first wave compared to the second are likely due to the restriction of testing to highly vulnerable sub-populations, e.g., nursing home residents.

Fig. 2. Counterfactual predictions of cumulative neurodegeneration-related diagnosis risks. Top vs. bottom: First vs. second infection wave. Left vs. right: Pre-pandemic controls vs. controls with negative test in the same reference period.

4 Preliminary Conclusion and Outlook

Unlike previous studies [4, 5], we do not find reported infections with SARS-CoV-2 to increase the risk of neurodegeneration-related diagnosis in the UK Biobank within the first two years. In the future, all analyses will be re-run on additional datasets, e.g., Danish register data and commercial data from the US, with a follow-up period up to almost the present day. It is possible that longer follow-up and larger sample sizes still reveal significant effects. If we are also able to identify high-risk patients with more individualized causal machine learning models (taking the whole medical history of patients' electronic health records into account), SHAP analysis will be run and paired with existing knowledge bases to find epidemiological (diagnoses, medications in patient history) and molecular (e.g., pathways, genes) risk factors.

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